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CONTENTS

Welcome message	1
Editorial Board	3
Meeting Programme	5
Meeting Abstracts	37
Author Index	129
Call for Papers	135
Sponsors	137

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TRANSCATHETER MITRAL VALVE REPLACEMENT: FROM EUREKA TO BENCH TO MARKET

Lucian Lozonschi

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Alain Cribier has capitalized on earlier ideas of replacing one's valve by means of catheters without cardiopulmonary bypass and showed the world its feasibility by performing the first human procedure in 2002. The field of Transcatheter Aortic Valve Replacement (TAVR) has since taken off and recently became an accepted treatment for severe aortic stenosis in patients at high and intermediate risk for surgical replacement. While the interest of replacing diseased mitral valves by catheter means is as old that of TAVR's, the transcatheter mitral valve replacement (TMVR) field has not experienced a similar boom due to the complexity of anchoring and securing a valve stent right in the middle of the heart without any adjacent rigid support structures such as aorta. This is a journey from the enlightening ideas for anchoring a mitral valve stent to securing intellectual property and tribulations of understanding the results of animal studies and finding the proper ways of advancing valve development. Working with Tendyne Medical, a startup company that had just one employee, its CEO until it assembled over 50 talented individuals before its swift acquisition by Abbott was not only a medical and engineering bending of the mind but also a course in leadership and entrepreneurship.

TECHNICAL TIPS AND TRICKS FOR THE HEART VALVE SURGERY THROUGH A MINI-STERNOTOMY APPROACH

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Objective: The aim of this study was to report on our experience after 7 years of practicing partial upper median sternotomy in surgery of cardiac valves and to present technical tips and tricks when using this approach.

Methods: The study included all the patients who underwent minimally invasive cardiac valve surgery through the partial upper median sternotomy, during the period from December 2008 to September 2015. We analyzed the data on mean age of patients, type of valve surgery (aortic or mitral) they underwent, postoperative day of extubation, mean extracorporeal circulation time, mean duration of hospital stay (and postoperative hospital stay), as well as on occurrence of postoperative complications (bleeding that required surgical revision or drainage of pericardium, surgical wound infection, CVI, and instability of sternum that required resuture).

Results: During the observed period, in the Institute for Cardiovascular Diseases of Vojvodina, 96 mini-sternotomies were performed, with 92 aortic valve replacements (95,83%), of which 88 (91,67%) due to aortic valve stenosis, and 4 (4,17%) due to aortic valve insufficiency; and 4 mitral valve replacements (4.17%), of which 1 (1,04%) due to mitral valve stenosis, and 3 (3,12%) due to mitral valve insufficiency. The mean age of the patients was 65.57±10.21 years - 42 (43.75%) were females, and 54 (56.25%) were males. On the day of operation 50 (52.08%) patients were extubated; 41 (42.71%) were extubated on the first postoperative day; 2 (2.08%) were extubated on the second postoperative day; and 1 (1.04%) patient was extubated on the seventh postoperative day (2 patients were not extubated). On the average, time of 0.52 days (12.5 hours) passed from operation to extubating of the patients. Mean extracorporeal circulation time was 93.56±30.36 minutes. Mean duration of hospital stay was 18.68±11.07 days (postoperative hospital stay was 11.86±6.75 days). Postoperative complications included: 2 (2.08%) surgical revisions of bleeding and 2 (2.08%) drainages of pericardium; 2 (2.08%) surgical wound infections; 3 (3.12%) CVI; and 1 (1.04%) resuture of sternum. Conversion to total median sternotomy was performed on 3 (3.12%) patients. Death in perioperative period occurred in 2 (2.1%) cases.

Conclusions: Partial upper median sternotomy still represents an optimal surgical method for interventions on the cardiac valves (especially aortic valve) and whole ascending aorta, with a few significant advantages compared to the surgical approach of total median sternotomy.